

LESSON-RESEARCH IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

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Annotation: The article reveals the methodology for organizing and conducting a research lesson in mathematics, built on the basis of competency-based and activity-based approaches.

Key words: competence-oriented education, organizational forms of training, mathematics lesson, general ability to solve plot problems.

Introduction. The need to orient the school to rapidly changing living conditions led to the introduction of a competency-based approach. Its implementation in modern didactics and primary education methods is considered as a way to ensure the quality of education and is associated with the practical focus of the process, the creation of prerequisites for the step-by-step management of the formation of students' educational achievements [4, 6, 7].

Competence-oriented education is based on a number of didactic means, which include organizational forms of training - mechanisms for streamlining the educational process in relation to the positions of its subjects, as well as the completeness of the structural units of training in the assemblage [1, 3]. New approaches require solving pressing issues: in what form will educational activities take place, how to organize it to achieve competency-based results that allow students to act independently in educational and life circumstances on the basis of acquired experience [2, 4, 5].

Research conducted by scientists on the state of formation of subject competencies among students in mass experience noted that this process in domestic schools has not yet constituted a comprehensive practice [1, 2, 8].

The predominance of a knowledgeable approach to the choice of forms and methods of teaching in the current conditions does not contribute to active educational cognition, but determines the achievement of such results that “in most cases, secondary school students, having information and having experience in solving problems in a learning situation, do not know how to solve informal (tasks that go beyond the educational process, make decisions in difficult life situations” [3, 5].

Considering that competency-based education is inherently activity-personal [4], it is advisable during its organization to refer to activity-oriented methods, technologies and forms of training. The need to actualize such a problem led to the search for ways to solve it.

The choice of good organizational forms of educational activities for junior schoolchildren, the construction of their systems is one of the current problems of modern pedagogical science and practice. Issues of improvement and development of organizational forms of teaching various subjects were studied by domestic and foreign scientists (T. M. Baybara, Yu. K. Babansky).

Theoretical understanding of the problem of organizational forms of education in primary school based on the analysis of foreign experience and its use in the domestic educational space, the development and implementation into mass practice of a methodology for lessons in literary reading, the Uzbek language, mathematics, and natural sciences based on a competency-based approach were carried out by scientists [9, 10, 12].

Topical issues of teacher training methods for the implementation of competency-oriented teaching of junior schoolchildren were studied by scientists from higher pedagogical institutions - Ya. P. Kodlyuk, N. A. Gluzman, R. Ya. Romanishin, G. A. Anisimova. At the same time, the problem of the optimal

combination within a lesson, in particular in the practice of teaching mathematics, of active methods of organizing the activities of younger schoolchildren, favorable for the development of abilities and the formation of competencies, remains insufficiently studied [11, 13, 14].

The main form of teaching mathematics in elementary school is a lesson. Each lesson is designed according to the goal, and its content is subject to a number of tasks that ensure the achievement of the goal [16, 18]. The content and purpose of the lesson determine its type. According to the main didactic goal in didactics, lessons are distinguished in mastering new material; consolidation and application of knowledge, skills and abilities; repetition and generalization of knowledge and skills; verification and monitoring of learning outcomes. However, these types of lessons in their “pure form” are rarely implemented in teaching practice. Considering that the process of developing mathematical skills is quite complex and lengthy, even after introducing students to new elements of knowledge, we continue to form (develop, improve) previously acquired educational experience. Thus, we most often design combined lessons. The predominance of such lessons is determined by the need for continuous repetition associated with the peculiarities of the mental processes of primary school students.

An analysis of the mathematics curriculum shows that its effective part provides for educational achievements of a predominantly activity-based nature. This is especially clearly expressed in the description of the requirements of the content line “Plot problems”, where such results are in 1st grade - 72%, in 2nd - 78%, in 3rd - 91%, in 4th - 80% . This fact directs the teacher to the implementation of a special function of teaching the subject, associated primarily with the formation of students' methods of action (skills and skills), necessitates the use of an activity-based approach to the construction of mathematics lessons, the use of active methods within them. Most of all, this applies to lessons, the purpose of which is to develop the ability to solve plot-based mathematical problems.

By general ability to solve plot problems we mean a complex personal formation that is used in solving a problem using different (basic) methods and consists of the following number of skills:

- 1) carry out a substantive and content analysis of the task;
- 2) perform a logical-semantic analysis of the task;
- 3) draw up a representative model of the problem (it can be: a brief record of the problem in the form of a diagram or table, a drawing, a schematic drawing, a drawing, a diagram, etc.);
- 4) make an estimate of the expected result;
- 5) search for a way to solve the problem using analytical or synthetic considerations;
- 6) draw up a plan for solving a problem using the arithmetic method; in algebraic - make equations;
- 7) implement the found solution plan;
- 8) check the correctness of the permit;
- 9) correlate a new problem with previously solved ones, transform a given problem, generalize its mathematical structure;
- 10) study the problem using the method of configurations of its individual parts [17].

The formation of such a skill is achieved by solving a special system of educational tasks, aimed not at obtaining a solution to a separate problem, but at working out a specific action. In the process of developing the ability to solve story problems, the problem itself and its solution become the subject of meaningful analysis, research into the influence of changes in the condition of the problem on its solution. Research and partially search methods appear as the main way of teaching.

According to the methodological system of teaching students to solve problems, which is based on work of a research nature with interconnected plot tasks, it became necessary to introduce lessons of a special structure, similar to the stages of educational research. They differ from other types of lessons primarily in their increased focus on working on a series of problems that take up the majority of

the time. The results of long-term experience in implementing this methodological system have convinced us that working on a number of interrelated problems allows the student to achieve greater progress in acquiring a general ability to solve problems than what happens traditionally, when during the lesson children solve several different types of problems with dissimilar plots.

Since, with the dominance of work on tasks, some forms and types of tasks familiar to combined lessons remain on the periphery of attention, we conditionally called the described organizational form a research lesson.

The purpose of such a lesson is for students to discover new educational content in the process of interaction with the teacher. In teaching the solution of structured problems in grades 2-3, activity in research lessons is structured as follows: students solve a problem of a mathematical structure known to them - one whose solution is not difficult for them, and then they investigate either the influence of changing the condition on the solution tasks, or changing the question to solving a problem.

Conclusions. Thus, students learn to note connections between numerical data, between numerical data and the desired one, which influence the solution of the problem. Such work in lessons takes about half the time, while in grades 3 and 4 it lasts longer. However, you should not force the research process until students have gained experience of independent activity. From lesson to lesson, the study of interrelated tasks becomes understandable, familiar and conscious to students. Lessons-research have a clearer structure when work is carried out on typical tasks in the content of teaching in the third and fourth grades, which will be described in the next publication.

To summarize, we note that organizing students' research work requires more time and effort than completing tasks according to the model. However, these costs are subsequently compensated by the fact that students will be able to quickly and correctly solve any problems in the initial course, independently master new content, and discover new knowledge. In addition, the awareness and strength of their

learning achievements will increase, a sustainable interest in the subject will arise, and a feeling of success will arise.

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